

FOREST RESOURCES OF UZBEKISTAN

Teacher of the department of the Ecology **Gaybullaeva.M**

Teacher of the department of the Ecology **Usmonov. S**

Teacher of the department of the Ecology **Akramov.A**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7943586>

Annotation: It is important to create new varieties of fruit trees, shrubs and medicinal plants that are resistant to diseases and pests, adapted to the soil and climatic conditions of our republic.

Keywords: forests, flora and fauna, shrubs and medicinal plants, use of trees and shrubs

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 11.05.2017 No. PQ-2966 "On the organization of the activities of the State Forestry Committee", the Ugom-Chotkal State National Nature Park under the administration of the Tashkent Region Hokimation and it includes the Chotkal State Biosphere Reserve, Ohangaron and Burchmulla forestry farms, as well as irrigation forestry farms of the system of water management organizations of the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It was noted that the Republic of Forestry will be transferred to the system of the State Committee. Uzbekistan is located in the central part of Central Asia, mainly between Amudarya and Syrdarya. The distance between the northernmost point and the southernmost point of Uzbekistan is 925 km, and the distance between the westernmost point and the eastern point is 1400 km. The diversity of life is primarily connected with the diversity of plant and animal species on earth. Forests are the most biologically diverse areas on earth, and their protection is important.

In Uzbekistan, there are more than 180 plants included in the Red Book. In the process of using nature, people usually interfere with natural processes and do not think about the consequences. As a result, the natural habitat of plants is reduced, and the decline of these species is observed. Therefore, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated January 17, 2019 "On the regulation of the use of trees and shrubs on lands not included in the state forest fund and improvement of the permit procedure in the field of their use" was signed. The purpose of introducing such decisions is to protect the forest fund.

Reduction and deterioration of the forest area is related to the development of human society. In the primitive society, people took some of the things they needed from plants and caused it to change, albeit partially. Especially in densely populated areas of the globe, 2/3 of the forests were destroyed. As a result, the area of land on earth decreased by 500 million ha, and the steppe was turned into a desert.

Unplanned and irregular cutting of forests, in turn, caused a disturbance in the balance of nature and accelerated the process of the following negative consequences for human economic activity; soil erosion has accelerated, the regime of rivers and lakes has changed, their water has started to decrease, floods and floods have become more frequent, it has affected the microclimate, the area of migratory birds in deserts has expanded, etc.

Forests are very important in cleaning the air of our planet. Because 1 ha of forest cleans 18 million cubic meters of air. The air in the forest is 200 times cleaner than the air in the city. They also give a person cultural aesthetic pleasure.

The area of the forest fund in Uzbekistan is 5.3 million hectares, and the total forested territory is 2.37 million hectares, occupying 5% of the republic's land area.

In Uzbekistan, forests are located in their plains. The total fund of forests in the mountains of Uzbekistan is around 1.4 million hectares, of which 283.7 million hectares are covered with forests. Spruce, pistachio, walnut, apple, cherry, almond, hawthorn grow in these forests. The main forests in the mountains of Uzbekistan are located in mountain ranges such as Ugom, Piskom, Chotkal, Hisar, Turkestan, and Zarafshan.

Forests in the deserts of Uzbekistan mainly consist of black and white (haloxylon), sugarcane, (calligonum), acacia, etc., which strengthen the shifting sands.

The area of the total forest fund in the valleys of the Republic is about 210 thousand hectare. The total forested area is 13 thousand hectares. Forests protect riverbanks from erosion and erosion, stop sand erosion in oases, improve the microclimate of surrounding lands, and provide wood for constructions.

Studying the geographical location of the forest fund on a scientific basis By studying the geographical location of the forest fund, having complete information about the forest fund, the quantity and quality of wood in one or another part of a certain country possible This allows for rational use of forests. If the forests in the west and south of Russia, which are densely populated but have few forest resources, are cut down a lot, the forests in sparsely populated Siberia, the Far East, and the north of Europe are cut down less.

Measures to combat deforestation in wood preparation and processing are important in forest protection. Because in this, forest industrial objects are brought closer to raw materials and a combine is established that uses them in a complex way, as a result, it puts an end to the output of many wastes and allows to plant new seedlings instead of one-way cut forests. The State Forestry Committee is of particular importance in the implementation of forestry protection measures, and the State Forestry Committee has the main tasks and activities directions are as follows:

- conducting a unified state policy aimed at the comprehensive expansion of forest resources and their rational use in the field of forestry;
- Development of proposals for improvement of forest legislation and practical control of their compliance;
- organization of effective management of the forest fund and protected natural areas, establishment of forests, their restoration, protection, protection, rational and economical use of forests;
- to develop and implement measures to restore forests and increase surrounding forests in the republic, to organize the establishment of anti-erosion plantations on mountain slopes, ravines and abandoned lands;
- to study the forest fund, fauna and flora and to keep a strict account of them, to introduce scientific achievements and advanced experience into the practice of forestry management;

In conclusion, preventing the death of young saplings plays an important role in the protection of forest resources. first of all, it is necessary to organize Christmas tree celebrations in the new year in order to put an end to indiscriminate cutting of young forests that have not yet matured. Because in the outskirts of big cities, there are often cases of secretly cutting down forests made of elm and white pine on the eve of the New Year. The reason for the needless destruction of plants is the city's fairs organized in the spring. Because most of those who go out to rest break the branch of young flowering plants and make a "bouquet" and return to the city.

References:

1. Tursunov X.T., Rahimova T.U. Ekologiya . - T.: “Chinor ENK”, 2006.
2. Ergashev A. Umumiy ekologiya.- T.: “O‘zbekiston”, 2003.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasini Prezidentining 11.05.2017 yildagi PQ-2966-son “O‘rmon xo‘jaligi davlat qo‘mitasi faoliyatini tashkil etish to‘g‘risida”gi qarori.
4. Gaybullaeva M F “The Role Of Biomass In Saving Natural Resources” 2021/2/28 The American Journal of Horticulture and Floriculture Research page 6
5. Gaybullaeva M, Akramov A “Conservation of flora” Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 2021 page 195
6. Gaybullaeva M F «Influence of soil and climatic conditions of the experiment area in Fergana region on the weight of pea pods» Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research – 2022 page 89-92
7. Akramov A, Gaybullaeva M, Makhsudova G «Technology of grain-leguminous plant care in the hungry bush soils of Fergana region» 2021/5 EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research стр 5
8. Nazarov M, Gaybullaeva M “The importance of using legumes today” ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 2021 page 1127-1131
9. Nazarov M, Gaybullayeva M “Ekologik xavfsiz mahsulotlar yetishtirishda don dukkakli o‘simliklarni ahamiyati” актуальные вызовы современной науки 2019 page 7,8
10. Nazarov M, Gaybullaeva M Influence of ecological factors on photosynthesis processes in legumes. “Agro Science”Journal. 2020, 2nd appendix.
11. Gaibullaeva M “Methods of influence of soil powing on growth, plant development and accumulation of clubberry bacteria” EPRA International Journal of Research & Development (IJRD) oktyabr -2020. Pages 445-447
12. Гайбуллаева М “Адирли тупроқларда нўхотнинг тупроқ унумдорлиги ва азот тўпловчи бактерияларга таъсири” O‘zbekiston qishloq va suv xo‘jaligi. № 4. 2021 йил. 34 бет.
13. Назаров М, Гайбуллаева М “Дон дуккакли ўсимликларда фотосинтез жараёнларига экологик омиллар таъсири” № 2. Агро илм журнали. 30 бет
14. Tadjibayeva Lolaxon Akbarali qizi. (2023).
15. Khalmatova, S. M., Tadjibaeva, L., & Salimov, N. (2022). THE NEED TO DEVELOP INNOVATIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(10), 405-409.
16. Usmonov, M. A. J. O. S. (2022). FOTOSINTEZ MAXSULDORLIGIGA YEKISH MEYORI VA MA‘DAN O‘G‘ITLARINING TA‘SIRI. IJODKOR O‘QITUVCHI, 2(20), 170-174.
17. Tadjibayeva, Lolaxon Akbarali Qizi (2022). DRACAENA MARGINATAAYRIM BIOEKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA KO‘PAYTIRISH USULI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (10-2), 716-719.
18. Khalmatova, S. M., Tadjibaeva, L., & Salimov, N. (2022). THE NEED TO DEVELOP INNOVATIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(10), 405-409.

19. Tadjibayeva Lolaxon Akbarali qizi. (2023). SELITEB LANDSHAFTLARDA TUPROQLARNING IFLOSLANISHI VA CHIQINDILAR MUAMMOSI. Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies, 2(4), 515–517.
20. Tadjibayeva, L. (2023). BENJAMIN FIKUSI (FICUS BENJAMINA) O 'SIMLIGINING AYRIM BIOEKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNI YETISHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Наука и инновация, 1(4), 199-202.
21. Tadjibayeva, L., Xoldoralieva, S., Maxmudova, K., & Qurolova, F. (2023). SHAHAR SANOAT ZONALARINI KO'KALAMZORLASHTIRISHDA TERAQ (POPULUS L.) O'SIMLIGINING AHAMIYATI. Наука и инновация, 1(6), 16-18.
22. Tadjibayeva, L., Xoldoralieva, S., Maxmudova, K., & Qurolova, F. (2023). TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA EKOLOGIK MADANIYATNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MADANIY O'SIMLIKLARNING O'RNI. Наука и инновация, 1(5), 71-74.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY